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ABSTRACT

The paper provides an overview of modern methods of diagnosis and treatment of diabetic retinopathy and its complications. The advantages and disadvantages of individual treatment methods are listed. Indications and contraindications for specific types of treatment for diabetic retinopathy are described. Particular attention is paid to the surgical method of treatment, listing preoperative predictors of high or low functional and anatomical success. Brief summaries of each treatment method are provided.

Key words: Diabetic retinopathy, vitrectomy, laser

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DIABETIK RETINOPATIYANING ASORATLARI VA ULARNING YECHIMLARI**ANNOTATSIYA**

Maqolada diabetik retinopatiyani tashxislash va davolashning zamonaviy usullari va uning asoratlari haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan. Davolash usullarining afzalliklari va kamchiliklari sanab o'tilgan. Diabetik retinopatiyani davolashning muayyan turlari uchun ko'rsatmalar va qarshi ko'rsatmalar tavsiflanadi. Jarrohlik davolashga alohida e'tibor berilgan bo'lib, funktsional va anatomik muvaffaqiyat prediktorlari sanab o'tilgan. Har bir davolash usulining qisqacha tavsifi berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: diabetik retinopatiya, vitrektomiya, lazer

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ОСЛОЖНЕНИЯ ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ РЕТИНОПАТИИ И ИХ РЕШЕНИЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В работе приведен обзор современных методов диагностики и лечения диабетической ретинопатии и её осложнений. Перечислены преимущества и недостатки отдельных методов лечения. Описаны показания и противопоказания к конкретным видам лечения диабетической ретинопатии. Особое внимание уделено к хирургическому методу лечения, перечисляя дооперационные предикторы высокого или низкого функционального и анатомического успеха. Приведены краткие резюме по каждому методу лечения.

Ключевые слова: Диабетическая ретинопатия, витректомия, лазер

Diabetik retinopatiya (DR) diabet bilan og'rig'an bemorlarning hayot sifatiga sezilarli darajada ta'sir qiladi va rivojlangan mamlakatlarda mehnatga layoqatli yoshdagi (20-65 yosh) kattalarda ko'rish qobiliyatini yo'qotishning asosiy sababi bo'lib qolmoqda [1]. Hozirgi vaqtda 90 millionga yaqin diabetga chalinganlar DR bilan og'riydilar, shu jumladan 17 million proliferativ diabetik retinopatiya (PDR), 21 million diabetik makula shishi (DMSH) va 28 million DR bemorlar ko'rish qobiliyati uchun jiddiy xavf tug'diradi va ushbu tendentsiya 2025 yilga kelib profilaktik va terapevtik strategiyalarning samaradorligi yetarli emasligi sababli ikki baravar ko'payadi [2].

1991 yilda Jahon Sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti Koxer E. va Porta M. tomonidan taklif qilingan DR tasnifini ma'qulladi, bu to'g'ridan-to'g'ri oftalmoskopiya usuli bilan aniqlangan ko'z tubidagi strukturaviy o'zgarishlar ketma-ketligiga asoslangan. Ushbu tasnif DR ni uch bosqichga ajratadi: proliferativ bo'lmagan, preproliferativ va proliferativ DR [3].

DR asosidagi patologik o'zgarishlar o'zaro bog'liq bo'lgan uchta mexanizm orqali ko'rishning buzilishiga olib keladi. Birinchidan, ishemiyaga olib keladigan to'r parda perfuziyaning yo'qligi to'r parda funksiyani bevosita buzishi mumkin. Mahalliy ishemiya va gemato-retinal to'siqni yo'qolishiga javoban mahalliy yallig'lanish reaksiyasi paydo bo'ladi, bu bir nechta sitokinlarni, shu jumladan qon tomir endotelial o'sish omili-A (VEGF) ni faollashtirishni o'z ichiga oladi. VEGF darajasining oshishi ikkita qo'shimcha patologik jarayon orqali ko'rishning yomonlashishiga bevosita yordam beradi. Birinchidan, qon tomir endotelial o'sish omili-A (VEGF)ning patologik darajasi to'r parda tomirlarining yaxlitligini yanada buzadi, bu esa gematoretinal to'siqni yo'q qilishga va odatda tomirlar ichida joylashgan suyuqlik, lipidlar va oqsillarni to'r pardaga eksudatsiyasiga olib keladi. Bu jarayon diabet bilan bog'liq makula shishi (DMSH) deb ataladigan to'r pardaning qalinlashishiga olib keladi. Ikkinchidan, qon tomir endotelial o'sish omili-A (VEGF)ning patologik darajasi g'ayritabiiy angiogenezni (yangi qon tomirlarining rivojlanishi) – Neovaskulyarizatsiyani rag'batlantirishi mumkin. Ushbu patologik yangi tomirlar shishasimon bo'shliqqa optik shaffof shishasimon gelni tashkil etuvchi kollagen tarmog'i bo'ylab tarqaladi. Dastlab, bu tomirlar izolyatsiya qilingan, ammo vaqt o'tishi bilan traksion komponentlar ularga izolyatsiyalangan tomirlarga yopishadi. Ushbu tomirlar shishasimon tana bo'shlig'iga qon ketishiga olib keladi va traksion komponentlar qisqarishi va to'r pardoning ko'chiishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

DRni tashxislash usullari

Ko'z tubini bilvosita oftalmoskopiya yordamida ko'rish mumkin bo'lsa-da, davolash usullari ko'pincha qo'shimcha sezgir usullardan foydalangan holda tanlanadi, shuning uchun ko'pincha multimodal tasvirlash DRni davolashda qo'llaniladi. Invaziv bo'lmagan OKT DMSHni davolashning asosi bo'lib, DMSH mavjudligini tasdiqlash, to'r pardaning qalinligini aniqlash va davolash samaradorligini baholash uchun ishlatiladi. Har qanday DR bilan og'riqan bemorlar, odatda, barcha holatlarda bo'lmasa ham, OKT tekshiruvidan o'tadilar. Bundan tashqari, OKT to'r pardaning alohida qatlamlarini ko'rish uchun foydali prognostik vosita sifatida ishlatilishi mumkin. Ko'z tubining rangli fotosurati, fluoresent angiografiyasi (FAG), Ultra keng burchakli tasvirlash (UKBT) va OKT angiografiyasi (OKTA) qo'shimcha usullar bo'lib, ular orqali qimmatli ma'lumotlarni ham olish mumkin. Shifokorlar DR rivojlanishini kuzatish uchun dinamikadagi tasvirlarni solishtirishlari va tasvirlardan shifokorlar va bemorlarni o'qitish vositasi sifatida foydalanishlari mumkin. Angiografiya yordamida to'r parda perfuziya va qon tomirlarda qon oqishini baholash mumkin. Makula va ko'z orqa qismidagi o'zgarishlardan tashqarida shifokorlar ko'pincha retinopatiyaning og'irlik darajasini to'liqroq tushunish va davolanishni tanlash uchun UKBT tasviridan foydalanadilar. OKTA an'anaviy FA uchun zarur bo'lgan tomir ichiga bo'yoq yuborish in'ektsiyasidan foydalanmasdan to'r parda tomirlarning invaziv bo'lmagan yuqori aniqlikdagi tasvirlarini taqdim etadi va klinik tadqiqotlarda ham, kundalik amaliyotda ham tobora ko'proq qo'llanilmoqda.

PDRni davolash usullari.

Bugungi kunda mavjud PDRni davolashning asosiy usullari masalan, to'r parda panretinal retinal lazer koagulyatsiyasi (PRLK), qon tomir endotelial o'sish omili-A (VEGF) ingibitori (anti-VEGF) preparatlarni intravitreal qo'llash va vitrektomiya amaliyoti turli tamponadalar bilan qo'llanilib kelinmoqda. Ushbu muolajalarning har biri o'ziga xos afzalliklari va kamchiliklariga, shuningdek ko'rsatmalar va qarshi ko'rsatmalarga ega. Lazer koagulyatsiyasi saratonni rentgen nurlari yordamida davolashga o'xshaydi, intravitreal anti-VEGF yoki kortikosteroidlarni yuborish esa kimyoterapiyaga o'xshaydi. Ushbu ikkita yondashuv ko'pincha birgalikda qo'llaniladi.

1970-yillardagi tadqiqotlar diabetik retinopatiyaning PRLK orqali davolash asosiy usul sifatida qo'llanilganligi aniqladi va natijalari bilan solishtirganda davolashdan keyin ko'rlikning keskin pasayganligini ko'rsatdi [4]. PRLK bugungi kunda PDRni davolashning asosiy usuli bo'lib qolsa-da, bu usulning ham o'ziga xos kamchiliklari va asoratlari bor usul hisoblanadi. To'r parda to'qimasi kuydiriladi va shu to'qimada chandiq hosil bo'ladi. Ushbu jarayon ko'pincha PDRga xos bo'lgan proliferativ jarayonning rivojlanishini to'xtatsa-da, u salbiy oqibatlariga olib kelishi mumkin. Birinchidan, ko'pchilikning fikriga ko'ra, PRLK umrbod proliferative jarayonni to'xtatadigan usul emas. Masalan, dastlabki bosqichda PRLKni anti-VEGF farmakoterapiyasi bilan (DRCR Network Protocol S), qo'llanilganda, 5 yillik kuzatuv davomida PRLK bilan davolangan ko'zlarning yarmidan ko'pi qo'shimcha PRLKni talab qilganligini ko'rsatdi [4]. Ikkinchidan, PRLK periferik ko'rish sohasidagi nuqsonlarga, qorong'ilikdagi ko'rishning va kontrast sezgirligining yo'qolishiga olib kelishi mumkin. PRLKning asosiy afzalligi shundaki, davolanish doimiy. PRLK lazer energiyasidan foydalanilgan holda doimiy chandiq hosil qiladi. Shunday qilib, ba'zi ko'zlarni bitta yoki hech bo'lmaganda kerakli miqdordagi PRLK yordamida yetarli darajada davolash mumkin.

Anti-VEGF farmakoterapiyasi bilan davolashning asosiy afzalligi shundaki, u PRLKning olib kelishi mumkin bo'lgan asoratlardan holi hisoblanadi. Bu ko'rish maydoniga kamroq, ammo progressiv yo'qolishiga olib keladi. Anti-VEGF farmakoterapiyaning salbiy tomoni preparatning farmakokinetikasi vaqtinchalik biologik ta'siri bilan bog'liq bo'lib, bemorning tashriflari va davolanish davomiyligining uzayishiga olib keladi. DRCR Network Protocol S randomizatsiyalangan 5 yil davomidagi kuzatuvlarida PDRli ko'zlar anti-VEGF davolanish uchun o'rtacha 43 ta, PRLK uchun esa xuddi shunday bemorlar orasida 21 ta klinik tashrifni talab qilishini aniqladi. Bundan tashqari, AntiVEGF bilan davolash yuki birinchi yildan keyin kamaygan bo'lsa-da, ko'pchilik (63-75%) ko'zlar 5-yil davomida har yili takroriy dozani talab qiladi, 43% esa davolanishning beshinchi yilida to'rt yoki undan ortiq in'ektsiyani talab qiladi [4]. Bundan tashqari, VEGFGA qarshi terapiya bilan davolash yuki birinchi yildan keyin kamaygan bo'lsa-da, ko'pchilik (63-75%) ko'zlar 5-yil davomida har yili takroriy dozani talab qiladi, 43% esa davolanishning beshinchi yilida to'rt yoki undan ortiq inyeksiyani talab qiladi [4].

QD bor bo'lgan bemorlarni ayniqsa davolash rejimiga rioya qilishi bilan bog'liq muammolar keng tarqalgan. DRCR Network Protocol Sning prospektiv tadqiqotida, atigi 66 foiz tirik bemorlarning 5 yil ichida davolanish yakuniga yetgani kuzatildi. 4 yil davomida kuzatilgan 2000 dan ortiq PDR bemorlarini tahlil qilish shuni ko'rsatdiki, ularning taxminan 25% i 12 oydan ko'proq vaqt davomidagi kuzatuvda, xech bir sababsiz yo'qolgan. Tadqiqotlar shuni korsatdiki, bemorlarning yoshi, irqi va o'rtacha yalpi daromadi ko'rikka qay darajada vaqt ajratishiga to'g'ridan to'g'ri bog'liqligi aniqlandi [5].

Jarrohlik davolash usullari

1980-yillarda diabetik vitrektomiyaning asosiy ko'rsatkichlari aniqlangan va bugungi kunda ham bir xil darajada dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda (bu shishasimon tanadagi qo'pol so'rilmaydigan xiralanishlar (destruksiya)ni olib tashlash va vitreoretinal traktsiyani olib tashlash) [6].

Vitrektomiya amaliyoti uchun makulaning tortilishi bilan to'r pardaning traksion ko'chishi (TPTK) vitrektomiya uchun eng keng tarqalgan ko'rsatma hisoblanadi va asboblardan hamda usullarning yaxshilanishiga qaramay, bu murakkab jarrohlik amaliyoti bo'lib qolmoqda. TPTK patofiziologiyasi qon tomir epitsentrlaridan boshlanadigan vitreoretinal adgeziyaga bog'liq, shuning uchun operatsiyani rejalashtirishda orqa gialoid membrananing konfiguratsiyasini batafsil baholash muhimdir. Keng vitreoretinal adgeziya bo'lgan ko'zlarda qayta proliferatsiya xavfi yuqori va ko'rish o'tkirligini tiklanishi bilan bog'liq natijalar yomonroq bo'lishi mumkin [7]. Shishasimon tanani to'r pardadan iloji boricha periferiyaga qadar ajratilishi muhim hisoblanadi. 25 va 27 G kichik kalibrli – vitrektomiya tizimlari tobora ommalashib bormoqda va an'anaviy 20 va 23 kalibrli nisbatan afzalliklarga ega. Kichik kalibrli tizimlar operatsiya vaqtini, bemorning noqulayligini, konyunktiva shikastlanishini kamaytiradi va tiklanish vaqtini qisqartiradi [8]. Fibrovaskulyar to'qimalarning vaskulyarizatsiyasini kamaytirish uchun klapan portlari va operatsiyadan oldingi antiangiogen vositalar bilan birgalikda mikroinvaziv vitrektomiya tizimlari yangi jarrohlik usullarini ishlab chiqishga imkon berdi [9]. Vitrektomiya uchun kichikroq zondlar, ayniqsa 27 va 25 kalibrli vitreotomlar, asosiy to'r pardaning minimal harakati bilan daqiqada 10 000 ta kesish tezligi, shuningdek, kesish teshigining asbob uchiga yaqinligi, ko'pchilik preretinal membranalarni segmentlarga ajratish va nazorat ostida olib tashlash imkonini beradi, zondlarning kichik diametri zich to'qimalarga kirish va o'tmas disseksiya texnikasidan foydalanish imkonini beradi.

Ko'pgina jarrohlik amaliyotining muvaffaqiyatli o'tishi, qulay tizimdan foydalanishdan tashqari ishning murakkabligi hamda jarrohning malakasiga asoslanadi.

Vitreoshizis qolgan orqa gialoidni aniqlashni qiyinlashtiradi, shuning uchun ko'plab jarrohlar qoldiq kortikal qatlamini aniqlash uchun triamsinolonidan foydalanadilar. Jarrohlik asboblari va ko'nikmalari yaxshilanishi bilan murakkab holatlarda ham jarrohlik amaliyotlari qo'llanila boshlandi va retsidivlar chegarasi pasaydi [10, 11]. Vitreoretinal jarrohlikning yutuqlari bular: keng burchakli tasvirni yetkazib beruvchi tizimlar, ko'p portli yoritish tizimi, perftor organik birikmasi va silikon moyini o'z ichiga oladi. Silikon moyidan foydalanish, uzoq muddatli gaz tamponadasidan farqli o'laroq, vizual rehabilitatsiyani tezlashtirishi, tamponadani qo'llash gipotenzianing oldini olishi va takroriy qon ketish yoki rubeoz darajasini kamaytirishi mumkin [12, 13, 14]. Silikon moyining kamchilklariga kataraktaning erta rivojlanishi, to'liq vizual rehabilitatsiyaga erishish uchun moyini olib tashlash zarurati, lentasimon keratopatiyasining rivojlanishi (ayniqsa, moy shox parda bilan aloqa qilganda) va moyining emulgatsiyasi, so'ngra KIB (ko'z ichki bosimi)ni ko'tarilishi kiradi [15]. Moyini olib tashlash odatda moyning asoratlarini oldini olish uchun amalga oshiriladigan ko'zning jarrohlik amaliyoti hisoblanadi. Moyini muddatidan oldin olib tashlash to'r pardaning takroriy ko'chishi xavfi, shishasimon tanaga qayta qon ketishini o'z ichiga oladi.

Klinik ko'rsatmalar va natijalar

Diabetik retinopatiya uchun vitrektomiya amaliyotining tadqiqoti (DRVS) – qandli diabet bilan og'rigan bemorlarda yagona prospektiv randomizatsiyalangan usul vitrektomiyadir. DRVS kuzatuvlari shuni isbotladiki, vitrektomiyaning qo'llab-quvvatlovchi juda ko'p dalillarni hisobga olgan holda vitrektomiya jarrohlik usullarini takomillashtirish hamda keyinchalik keng qo'llash diabet asoratlarini oldini olish uchun muhim hisoblanadi.

TPTK makula sohasi zararlanishi bilan bo'lganda vitrektomiya amaliyotiga oldindan PRLK qilinganligi, shishasimon tanada qon ketishning va og'ir neovaskulyarizatsiyaning mavjud emasligi kabi qulayliklar ko'rish o'tkirligini tiklanish davomiyligi qisqarishiga olib keladi [16, 17]. Ko'rish o'tkirligining tiklanishi quyidagi holatlarga qarab bashorat qilishi mumkin: rangdor parda rubeozi va neovaskulyar glaukoma, vitreopapillyar traksiya, ko'rish o'tkirligining pastligi ($<5/200$), shuningdek TPTK yoki TPRK mavjudligi. Ushbu omillardan kamida bittasiga ega bo'lish ko'rish o'tkirligi pasayishi xavfini 1,5–3,9 baravar oshiradi [18]. ko'rish o'tkirligi pasayishi odatda to'r pardaning doimiy burmalari, makula ishemiyasi, kistasimon makula shishi yoki fotoreseptorlarning shikastlanishi tufayli yuzaga keladi. Operatsiyadan keyingi ko'rish o'tkirligi makula sohasi qalinligi biroz va tashqi chegaralovchi membrana hamda ellipsoid zonasining yaxlitligi o'zaro bog'liqdir [19].

Yangi ishlanmalar

O'nlab yillar davomida orqa gialoid membrana ko'chishini farmakologik induksiya qilish orqali vitreomakulyar traktsiyani uzishga erishish uchun ko'plab tadqiqotlar qilingan. Okriplazmin simptomatik vitreomakulyar traktsiyani davolash uchun tasdiqlangan, ammo muvaffaqiyat darajasi eng yaxshi 50% ni diabetisiz ko'zlarda tashkil qiladi. DMSH bilan og'rigan bemorlarda III bosqich sinovlari davom etmoqda, ammo DR bilan og'rigan bemorlarda orqa gialoid membrana va to'r pardoning ichki chegara membranasi o'rtasidagi kuchli yopishqoqlik kuchlari mavjudligi bu tadqiqotlarni ortga surilishiga sabab bo'lmoqda.

Butun dunyo jarrohlari tomonidan kichik kalibrli vitrektomiya 23, 25 va 27 kalibrli asboblardan foydalanilmoqda. Vitreotomlar, yorug'lik manbalari, lazer zondlari yanada takomillashtiriladi va ko'p funksiyali asboblarning yangi turlari ishlab chiqilishi mumkin.

Vitrektomiyada intraoperativ optik kogerent tomografiya (OKT) fibrovaskulyar membranalar ostidagi to'qima qatlamlarini olib tashlash va qoldiq membranalar mavjudligini aniqlashga imkon beradi.

Xulosa

So'nggi qirq yil ichida diabetik retinopatiya asoratlarini davolash sezilarli darajada yaxshilandi. Operatsiyani oldindan oqilona rejalashtirish, jarrohlik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish, jarrohlikdan keyin bemorlar nazorati ushbu jarrohlik davolash usuli natijasida dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda. Har bir holat turli xil anatomiyaga ega bo'lganligi sababli, ularning har biri o'ziga xos individual yondashuvni talab qiladi. So'nggi yillarda jarrohlik operatsiyalari natijalari yaxshilandi va biz texnika hamda vositalarning doimiy rivojlanishi bilan bu tendentsiya davom etishiga ishonamiz.

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